

**Synthesis of Nickel Cobalt Manganese Sulphide (NCMS) by electrodeposition for
Supercapacitor applications**

Rohit Yadav, Mahesh Verma and Parasharam Shirage*

Discipline of Physics & Metallurgy Engineering and Materials Science, Indian Institute of
Technology Indore-453552. India.

*Author for correspondence

E-mail: pmshirage@iiti.ac.in

Abstract:

Nickel Cobalt Manganese Sulphide (NCMS) nanostructures have been prepared by simple and cost effective electrodeposition technique on Nickel (Ni) foam. The electrochemical measurements were investigated by using cyclic voltammetry and galvanostatic charging discharging. The large surface area of NCMS leads to high specific capacitance of 2581 F/g at a scan rate of 1mV/s by CV measurements and a capacitance of 5008.08 F/g by GCD measurements. The material shows an excellent stability of 57% at 3000 cycles at a current density of 100 A/g. Hence the NCMS nanostructured material demonstrate the application in efficient energy storage applications at high current density.

Keywords: Nickel Cobalt Manganese Sulphide (NCMS), electrochemical measurements, energy storage applications.